

Amicable Settlement In Sabangan, Mountain Province

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Abstract

This study describes the practice of amicable settlement in Sabangan, Mountain Province. It specifically looked into the extent of implementation of different activities in the amicable settlement, the perceived effectiveness of the practice, and the experiences of the parties involved, and the community people in the administration of the amicable settlement. The qualitative-quantitative method was used to gather data through questionnaire, interview, and focus group discussion. It was found that necessary actions are justly applied to address issues and conflict. However, some members of the lupon do not actively participate in dispute resolution and are not thoroughly aware on the provisions of the KatarungangPambarangay Law, which is necessary and a guide in an amicable settlement. On the other hand, parties involved and witnesses are moderately satisfied with the accused's compliance with the penalty imposed during the settlement.

Introduction

a. Background of the Study

Restorative justice is applied in most parts of the world to resolve conflict and restore a peaceful relationship in a community. For example, in England during ancient times, the Normans established the "Court Leet" (years 1066-1284) to handle local legal matters in all communities that looked after matters of purely local interest and petty village nuisances. It is a process for resolving crime by addressing the harm done to the victims, holding the offenders accountable for their actions, and engaging the community to resolve that conflict. The head of the Court Leet was the "Comes Stable," which means "Master of the House." The King also appointed the Comes Stable." to keep peace and order in a specific area.

In the People's Republic of China, a body called Peoples Conciliation Committee is in charge of settling disputes and minor criminal cases through conciliation. Its counterpart in the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic is the Comrades Court, which sanctions certain forms of anti-social behavior or minor importance, not meriting the attention of regular courts.

In Japan, informal means of dispute resolution through extrajudicial reconciliation and conciliation are being resorted to carrying over the Tokugawa legal System, which prominently features conciliation among members of a "kumi" (town or town or village) through the intervention of the respective family heads. They also use compensation settlement to repair the harm and apologize for preserving unity and promoting peace and order in wider communities (Fanao, 2019).

In the Philippines, before the Spanish colonization, its inhabitants had already re-solved disputes among the tribe members. The people afforded elders in the community high respect, and disputes were brought before the village elders (Zaide, 1994). People regarded by the community with utmost respect and credibility play the role of mediators or arbiters to address disputes in their early stages, thereby preventing the escalation to a more violent phase where the role of traditional mediators became effective. The power exercised by the elders in resolving conflict was extensive. They functioned to examine the evidence, evaluate testimonies, render judgment and define the penalties for the offense to preserve or restore community relationships.

The practice was institutionalized in 1978 when President Ferdinand Marcos promulgated the P.D. 1508 or the KatarungangPambarangayLaw, which was amended by Republic Act 7160 in 1991, also known as the Local Government Code. Under RA 7160, all offenses that the law prescribes a maximum penalty of imprisonment not exceeding one year or a fine of not over five thousand pesos (P5,000.00) are subject to barangay conciliation prior re-course thereto is a pre-condition before filing a complaint in court or any government offices. In addition, the Supreme Court even encourages the settlement of minor cases in the barangay to help them de-clog the numbers of cases filed in court.

Chapter VII, Book III, and Title I, section 399-422 of the said law embodied the amendment of the KatarungangPambarangay Law. This law embraces the concept of amicable settlement of disputes in the barangay level, through a group of persons collectively participated in by Lupon, elders, and barangay officials in which the Punong Barangay act as the head. In other words, this is the law that institutionalizes the *areglosystem* or amicable settlement.

Amicable settlement is a process of settling disputes within the barangay level, which is participated by disputing parties, the barangay officials, Lupon members as mediators or conciliators, and arbitrators. This was done through face-to-face communication and agreement of the disputing parties with the presence of a punong barangay, lupon member, or an elder to resolve a conflict.

The practice of amicable settlement played a significant role in de-clogging cases filed in court and facilitated the speedy administration of justice (Benter, 2016 & Valera, 2008); it values the Filipino traditions on settling disputes. Thus, Barangay Lupon, elders and officials in charge of the administration of justice at the barangay level, should be aware of how vital their roles and functions are. Their decision-making capacity is significant in attaining justice and the preservation of order within the barangay level.

Parties need to be assertive and vigilant but honest in an amicable negotiation. It was expected that if one party is timid and the other is vocal, the issue might be reversed. The intention of this practice is very noble, that is, to solve disputes where both disputants will earnestly come up with a solution. Thus, this process aspires that both parties develop honesty, respect, humility, and forgiveness. The same is true with the implementers of the practice; it is necessary that they should be fair and wise- decision-makers.

The barangay is a significant avenue for the administration of justice, whereby barangay officials and barangay have a significant role in preserving peace and order. Barangay law enforcers have a crucial role in delivering justice and preserving peace and order in the barangay. Their effectiveness and efficiency are where a true conciliation lies.

In Upper Sabangan, before the passage of the P.D.1508, the traditional system was, usually done with the conflict being tackled by a council of elders. Customarily, this group was given the ultimate authority to hear and decide grievances, (Pagandiyon, 2009). This is in line with the indigenous ways of constituting the council of elders as now provided for by the Indigenous People's Right Act or the R.A. 8371.

With the creation of the P.D. 1508, the role of elders was absorbed by the lupon members where most members are elderly headed by the punong barangay as the primary dispute mediators. Upper Sabangan had been applying for amicable settlement in most crimes and offenses despite the presence of professionals and accessibility of courts.

According to the records on file of every barangay, different cases were resolved at the barangay level from simple theft, defamation, physical injury, drunkenness, land dispute, pine tree disputes, animal dispute, threat, and malicious mischief. As per record, sanctions are rendering community services, *destierro*, or paying fines in cash or kind.

In the case of three barangays, sexual harassment, rape, and vehicular accident resulting in a homicide which is not supposed to be heard in the barangay, were also amicably settled because parties preferred to resolve it through local officials. As a result, no court re-course was made. Settlement may take an hour negotiation, but there had been cases that took two or three hearings before an agreement had been reached because parties do not immediately agree with the negotiation.

Thereby, this study examined the practice of amicable settlement in Upper Sabangan, Mountain Province. It looked into the extent of implementation of the different activities in the conduct of amicable settlement, recognized the perceived effectiveness of amicable settlement in Upper Sabangan, and explored the experiences of the parties involved and community people in the administration of the amicable settlement. Therefore, this study will somehow be instrumental in enriching activities in the conduct of amicable settlement and heighten fulfillment of parties involved and the community on the said practice.

b. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework:

The overall concept in which this study is anchored is upon the idea of Peacemaking Criminology (Pepinsky&Quinney, 1991). Peacemaking criminologists are concerned about minimizing social inequality and placing the responsibility on offenders.

This theory agrees that arresting and putting a criminal in jail will not solve the root causes. Instead, talking out the causes of one's action will address the problem and transform a man into a better person. It is when people make and keep agreements that trust grows (Claassen&Claassen, 2008).

Another is the Control Theory, as proposed by Travis Hirschi, which assumes that the desire to commit a crime is natural to all human beings. Control theories begin with the view that crime is simply the consequence of the rational and self-interested nature in which everyone is born. People can all naturally anticipate the benefits and costs of their actions. Moreover, they choose to behave in whichever way is beneficial to them. Their self-interested nature means that they consider costs and benefits related specifically to their pleasure. Therefore, societies create formal and informal methods of enforcing rules to protect order and ensure a smoothly running community.

Timlin (2011) had the concept that the community is where the responsibility of problem-solving and conflict resolution should first fall. The most meaningful lesson about conflict and its impact on friends, neighbors, and community can be best attained.

Conflict management is predicated upon the idea that diagnosing the situation is necessary as a basis for action. There is no best way to manage conflict under all conditions, but there are optimal ways of managing it under certain conditions. An important aspect of conflict management is considering alternative ways of managing conflict and the kind of situation in which each of these alternatives might be expected to be most effective. In addition, Cognitive Theory, as cited by Pesase (2017), states that cognitive development is a comprehensive theory about the nature and development of human intelligence. It deals with the nature of knowledge itself and how humans gradually acquire and use it. Being aware of the positive effects of an amicable settlement, as less costly and facilitates a quick resolution, people give in to the practice.

Method

Research Design

This study used a qualitative-quantitative design where questionnaire, interview, observation, and descriptive method were utilized.

Locale of the Study

This research was conducted in Upper Sabangan, Mountain Province. Multi-stage sampling was utilized to identify the respondents. Five (5) barangays, or 55% of the total barangay, were chosen to represent the study. The first stage used a simple random sampling through draw lots in selecting five barangays. Next, stratified sampling was used, specifically the proportional allocation distribution, to get a sufficient number of respondents per barangay to represent their perception of the extent of implementation of activities during amicable settlement. The barangays chosen were Barangay Bun-ayan, Capinitan, Camatagan, Bao-angan, and Namatec. Then, purposive sampling was applied for the barangay law enforcers and the parties involved from each barangay. For the variable community, the Slovin formula was utilized in computing the sample size (n) of community respondents.

Participants of the Study

The respondents were the parties involved (complainant, respondent/accuse), barangay law enforcers (Barangay officials and Lupon members), and community people. They are all of legal age and are presently residing in the barangays in Upper Sabangan. As to the community people, 81 was taken from barangay Bun-ayan, 72 from Capinitan, 32 from Camatagan, 55 from Bao-angan, 67 from from Namatec with a total of 307 participants. For the Barangay Law Enforcers, 15 was taken from Bun-ayan, 15 from Capinitan, 15 from Camatagan, 19 from Bao-angan, and 16 for Namatec with a total of 80 participants. As to the parties involved, 16 were taken from Bun-ayan, 8 from Capinitan, 15 from Camatagan, 12 from Bao-angan, and 15 from Namatec, with 66 participants. In all, barangay Bun-ayan has 112 participants, Capinitan has 95, Camatagan has 62, Bao-angan has 86 and Namatec has 86 participants.

Among the respondents, five (5) parties involved and five (5) community people were interviewed regarding their experiences on amicable settlement. Experience, as referred to in this study, is the respondents' observations and feelings when they were involved in the amicable settlement process in their respective barangays.

Instrumentation

A questionnaire checklist was used to gather data on the extent of implementation of the different activities in the conduct of amicable settlement. This was based on the Katarungang Pambarangay Law or R. A. 7160 and the book of Macalingay titled *State-of-the-Art-Katarungang-Pambarangay-Law in Besao Mountain Province*. Interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were used to determine the perceived effectiveness of amicable settlement in Upper Sabangan and the experiences of the parties involved and community people in the administration of the amicable settlement.

Data Collection

After the permission to conduct research was granted, the researcher sought the permission of the Municipal Mayor of Sabangan, Mountain Province, Municipal Local Government Officer, and different Punong Barangay. In addition, the researcher sought the consent of residents from different barangays and their approval to answer the questionnaire and interview. The researcher oriented the respondents that confidentiality of their answers is strictly observed. No answers and names, especially sensitive matters, were divulged in any part of the study for security and safety concerns. Those willing to participate in the study were the ones given the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered personally by the researcher, collected after several days. After which, the

responses were tallied correctly, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly. Follow up interview was used to strengthen the answers obtained from the questionnaire.

On the other hand, the interview guide was used to elicit the participants' answers and perceptions on the effectiveness of the amicable settlement and their experiences in the administration of the procedure. Finally, the referral method was used to determine the participants of the study. The responses were noted and recorded. It was then coded and analyzed for the discussion.

Treatment of Data

The data on the extent of implementation of different activities in the conduct of amicable settlement was subjected to basic measures of frequency counts and weighted means.

Thematic analysis was employed to determine the perceived effectiveness of the amicable settlement and the experiences of the parties involved and community people in the administration of the amicable settlement. From the interviews and FGD, the researcher used the descriptive method to elicit codes and themes for discussion.

Results and Discussion

Extent of Implementation of Different Activities in the Conduct of Amicable Settlement in Upper Sabangan, Mountain Province

The grand mean revealed that most activities that conduct amicable settlements are not implemented faultlessly. However, the highest mean was information dissemination to the barangay officials and lupon as to the date of hearing interpreted as very much implemented. The findings implied that all stakeholders were notified of the schedule of hearing. With the presence of cellular phones, barangay officials can quickly contact one another, and since barangay residents know each other, they can send/relay messages or notices to neighbors.

Table 1. Extent of Implementation of Activities in Amicable Settlement

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Summoning the respondent after a complaint is filed.	2.95	Moderately Implemented
2. Giving notice as to the schedule of hearing to the complainant after a complaint is filed.	3.15	Moderately Implemented
3. Information dissemination to the barangay officials and lupon as to the date of the hearing.	3.31	Very Implemented Much
4. Dismissal of the complaint in the absence of the complainant without justifiable reason.	2.94	Moderately Implemented
5. Dismissal of respondent's counterclaim if he does not appear on the settlement without justifiable reason.	2.88	Moderately Implemented
6. Active participation of all lupon members on the facilitation of amicable settlement.	2.72	Moderately Implemented
7. Coming-up/arriving at an accepted agreement.	2.91	Moderately Implemented
8. Fair imposition of penalty or sanctions by the barangay law enforcer.	2.73	Moderately Implemented
9. Compliance of the respondent/accuse on the penalty or sanction on the amicable settlement.	2.71	Moderately Implemented
10. Putting into writing all settlements done in the barangay.	3.10	Moderately Implemented
Total Mean	2.94	Moderately Implemented

Second to the highest is giving of notice as to the schedule of hearing to the complainant after filing a complaint. It shows that there had been only a rare case where the complainant was notified at the very moment of the hearing where allegedly a barangay official was tasked to inform the complainant. However, due to negligence, the complainant was not informed earlier.

Third in rank to the highest is writing all settlements done in the barangay, which implies that people in Upper Sabangan document the result of any negotiation because it is evidence that can prove that an agreement transpired among parties or a case had been settled.

Third to the lowest mean is the active participation of all lupon members in the facilitation of amicable settlement. In an interview with some barangay officials, not all lupon members are informed on the settlements, to add that some lupon cannot confidently involve themselves during the negotiation because there were no seminars conducted for them to be exposed and to be well-versed on their functions.

The first–two indicators that garnered the lowest mean are the respondents' compliance/accuse on the penalty or sanctions imposed and fair imposition of penalty or sanctions by the barangay law enforcers.

The compliance of the accused on the penalty implies that some barangay law enforcers are lax on the enforcement of penalties agreed. They laid down the decision, but there are cases of no persistent command towards the guilty to pay monetary punishments or immediate replacement of stolen property. Giving a lot of time allowances and considerations to the guilty party to indemnify their victim sometimes ends up in useless negotiation, especially if no follow-up is done to determine if compliance is initiated.

There had been an epoch where the stealing of animals was rampant. Culprits were known, but not one animal was replaced or paid. There had been a case of stealing money, but it took a long period before the payment of the amount was settled. Another reason why some respondents do not seriously comply with the punishment is that the barangay officials do not enforce or are not familiar with applying a writ of execution of the penalty in court if the guilty party is reluctant to abide by the agreement. Furthermore, they can turn over the case to the court after six months if the accused is still non-compliant and let the court execute the punishment. Consequently, in a settlement done in one barangay, a retired policeman suggested that if the accused will not produce at once the agreed amount to indemnify the victim, the agreements should not be put into writing, that is to ensure the offender will pay the amount immediately. It was found out effective because the respondents employed all means to compensate the victim.

As to fair imposition of penalty or sanctions by the barangay law enforcers, there are some circumstances that complaints are treated unequally. For example, there had been cases of the same offense committed, like drunkenness and gossiping. However, different amounts of penalties were imposed. In addition, there had been cases of physical injury where both parties were at fault. However, only one party was decided to shoulder the expenses during the negotiation, and the other party was only advised. Furthermore, there had been cases of a pine tree and land dispute where bias among testimonies of barangay law enforcers on who are the owners was obviously manifested.

Some barangay law enforcers do not always apply careful judgment, stated by someone who was once involved in a settlement. Instead, relationships, "utangaloob," grudge, and political motives exist.

As uttered by one complainant, the statement goes as follows:

"Wada ay wadaladta nan mapabpaburancinekkandadiopisyalyalupon ay mande-sisyonkarkaro nu eelan da nan ipugao it esa ay nangibutoskendaida, kabagyan da unuesa ay mabigbig et adi da unaykumaliya".

[There is favoritism on how barangay officials and lupon decide on cases, especially if one party is their supporter during elections, a relative, or belongs to a known family, they cannot just talk against that person.]

This is in line with the Social Contract Theory, which believes that the bonds people form to pro-social values, pro-social people, and pro-social institutions control people's behavior. In the practice of amicable settlement, vigorous enforcement of punishments makes people comply.

Perceived Effectiveness of the Amicable Settlement in Upper Sabangan

1. Contributes harmony in the barangay. It shows that the people regard amicable settlement as a process to promote tranquility in the community (Timlin, 2011). This was proven by a case of physical injury committed by constituents from a different municipality, who mauled a minor resident from the locale due to a mistaken identity. Arbitrating the case helped preserve the good relationship among the families and between the two municipalities. In Bauko, Mountain Province, amicable settlement is a practice that bind the residents closer (Pagandiyan, 2009).

This is comparable with the study of Budaden (2006) where the bodong system or peace pact agreement in some municipalities or provinces like Kalinga Province and Eastern Mountain Province. These provinces used peace pact agreement in order to solve disputes and crime within the barangay or in between two municipalities; this proves to maintain peace and coordination in between them.

In Sadanga, they have the version of bodong called Pechen which is used to restore harmonious relationship between two warring tribes. According to a tribal elder of Betwagan, a go-between in the person of any government or non-government peace agent initiates the peace pact between the two warring tribes. If both agreed to choose “friendship” over war, the elders of each tribe will select to undergo peace pact agreement (Fanao, 2019).

In this finding the concept of restorative justice system is strongly evident since harmony in the barangay is reestablished between and among the parties involved (Timlin, 2011).

2. Strengthen community ties and values. The finding signifies that most respondents consider amicable settlement as a mechanism to penetrate good community relations and positive public attitudes. It was evident in cases of theft, libel, physical injury due to drunkenness, breach of contract, and public disturbance whereby guilty parties were given pieces of advice and other disciplinary actions in order to teach them good values to correct unacceptable behaviors and to enhance their behavior. This was affirmed by Arellano (2011) that amicably settling dispute preserves Filipino culture and strengthens family and community bonds.

3. Reinforce existing traditional customs and contribute to maintaining peace in the barangay. For example, in cases of physical assault, physical injury, public disturbance, and gossiping, if the perpetrator is wholeheartedly remorseful, they can directly ask the victim's forgiveness or submissively accept guilt during settlement and compromise with the aggravated party. It revealed that most of the residents view the old-aged practice in a settlement like *"tet-eya"* or direct communication solve conflict. Also, the concept of *"inayan"* or fear of the Creator makes parties utter true statements during settlements. This helps the offender readily admit his fault, aside from inculcating the values of repentance and forgiving. This is also true with the findings of Fanao (2019) that in Sadanga, people apply apology and forgiveness in their indigenous dispute resolution. It is also in consonance with the theory of the Peacemaking Criminology as proposed by Pepinsky and Quinney (1991), which stated that putting an offender in jail will not address the causes of the problem, but talking out the reasons will help and transform a man to become a better person. In Upper Sabangan, this is an essential consideration why people submit cases/complaints to the practice or advise concerned parties to undergo an amicable settlement.

Experiences of the Parties Involved and Community People in the Administration of Amicable Settlement

Based on the interviews, the following themes were derived from portraying the experiences of the parties involved and the community members in the administration of amicable settlement:

1. Fair chance to all parties to present their contentions. Parties were given an equal opportunity to tell their own stories or how they were affected by the issue. In addition, parties can narrate how the crime happened and defend or excuse themselves. This was substantiated by Zehr, H. (2002) that in the practice of restorative justice, “the process involves those who have a stake in a specific offense and to collectively identify and address harms, needs, and obligations, in order to heal things as right as possible.”

One party involved narrated the following:

Amin kami it kumali, ibagami nan side mi, nan naila mi, nan napasamakya nan rikna mi kalpasan di pasamak. Sinan ikkan di opisyalknlupon ay mandesisyon it mabalin ay mantawar kami nu talagayadi mi kaya nan ibaga da imulta or mabayadanngemwa-da mit nan talagay nu amu nay basolna it siaamin sin ibagandadilupon.

[All of us talk during negotiation, we explain what we saw and how things happened and how we felt after the event. As to how officials and lupon decide, we can appeal if we feel the fine imposed is too high, but some immediately accept the decision if they know it is their fault.]

2. Coming up/arriving at an acceptable agreement. All disputing parties who underwent the practice have a voluntary agreement. Parties realize the values of humility, confession, and repentance as the primary key for genuine reconciliation. Although, the ability of a mediator to negotiate, explain, and convince the disputing parties to agree also aid a lot for a successful amicable settlement. One Indigenous People's (I.P.) representative explained that there would be a peaceful and candid resolution if there were a fair and judicious decision.

Attributed to the elders and leaders is their ability to facilitate any negotiation because of their skill to explain well to the parties and convince them for the decision. In the end, no one should be holding bitter feelings. On the contrary, as explained by Abletes (2004), if parties were sufficiently enlightened about the positive results of forgiving and giving in, it would make litigants readily accept the settlement.

3. Lack of awareness on the coverage of KatarungangPambarangay Law (KPL). The participants, are not all mindful that heinous crimes such as rape and homicide should not be settled at the barangay level. This is consistent with the findings of Lafadchan et al. (2022) that rape is still being settled in the barangay level at

Mountain Province. However, it had been a practice that any case would be settled in the barangay for whatever crime, whether a simple violation or heinous, so long as the parties voluntarily submit to an amicable settlement. This was intensified by the lack of orientation of the barangay law enforcers on the different crimes covered by the KPL.

Based on the interview with one Punong Barangay, only one seminar for KatarungangPambarangay Law was conducted only at the provincial level. Hence, some barangay officials and lupon members are minutely aware of the cases covered by KPL, so those who did not attend had no other chances of knowing it, especially for the newly elected officials or newly appointed lupon members.

In a conversation with barangay officials, the researcher noted that the barangay officials expect the Municipal Local Government Office to sponsor seminars or training regarding the KatarungangPambarangay Law. On the other hand, the Office of the Municipal Local Government Operation Officer (MLGOO) is waiting for the barangay to request since the barangay will shoulder expenditures. Therefore, misunderstanding on who has the task to conduct such seminar or training is herein realized, hence posing a risk on the responsiveness of the barangay law enforcers as to their powers and functions due to lack of orientation or training.

Considering all the results, a summation of the study herein realized. First, the practice of amicable settlement has an excellent intention to immediately resolve disputes and crimes between friends, family, and neighbors. Where parties heartily come up with a solution with-out much cost, waste of time, and effort. It helps the law enforcers investigate criminals, bringing out culprits and relieving the court from docket congestion. Third, it aims to develop the values of honesty, repentance, and forgiveness among people.

Thence, the results infer that proper implementation of activities boils down to acceptable agreements in an amicable settlement. Moreover, the amicable settlement practice developed good relationships among community residents and enhanced the traditional practice of talking among family, neighbors, and town mates whatever conflict that arises.

Nevertheless, amicable settlement practices in Upper Sabangan support the Control Theory of Travis Hirshi, where fear of penalty to a certain degree prevents culprits from committing wrongdoing. Moreover, the people's respect and obedience to elders and value of self-discipline help on the participation of both parties in amicable settlements.

Conclusion

The groups of respondents in Upper Sabangan indicated that the activities in the conduct of amicable settlement are not totally implemented from the filing of cases until the final decision-making. However, participants perceived that the effectiveness of the practice helps bring harmony in the barangay, strengthening community ties, values and contributing to the maintenance of peace and order. The parties involved and the community people appreciate the performance of the barangay law enforcers in giving a fair chance to both parties in giving their contentions and coming up with an acceptable agreement. However, some barangay law enforcers are not always consistent in making fair decisions; and are not always strictly enforcing the penalty upon offenders.

Recommendations

1. The Municipal Government of Sabangan, in coordination with the DILG, LGU, and DOJ, may provide or sponsor regular seminars among the barangay officials and Lupon members at least twice a year. That is to discuss their powers and functions and enhance their knowledge on the provisions of the KPL.
2. Barangay Law Enforcers may apply maximum effort to settle all complaints with fairness and enforce prompt compliance of offenders on penalties agreed.
3. The LGU and DSWD may conduct a seminar on barangay law enforcers' personality development and human relations.
4. A standard penalty for specific offenses or violations may be included in barangay ordinances

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